

Sightseeing Passenger Transport Route
PICK-UP/DROP-OFF POINT
SPINOLA BAY
ST. JULIANS

TREES
tourism research
in economic environs
& society
the
vanguard
of tourism
research

PROFILING DIVE OPERATORS in Malta

PROFILING DIVE OPERATORS in Malta

This research forms part of the Green Bubbles RISE Project

Green Bubbles

This project has received funding from the EU's H2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 643712.

www.GreenBubbles.eu

TREES

tourism research

in economic environs

& society

the
vanguard
of tourism
research

TOURISM RESEARCH IN ECONOMIC ENVIRONS AND SOCIETY

North-West University
Potchefstroom Campus
Private Bag X6001
Potchefstroom
2520

+27 18 285 2331

+27 18 299 4140

/TREESNWU

www.NWU.ac.za/TREES

Lindie.duplessis@nwu.ac.za

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the following people and institutions:

- All the operators who were willing to make time during their busy schedule to participate in the research.
- In particular, Prof Martinette Kruger, who was on mobility in Malta in August 2016 and conducted all the interviews with the operators.
- Marie Skłodowska-Curie European Union's Horizon 2020 grant for funding this project.
- Cecile van Zyl for the language editing.

Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY	1
3. RESULTS	2
3.1 Demographic profile of the dive operators	2
3.2 Details of the dive operators	2
3.3 Key success factors	4
3.4 SWOT analysis	6
4. SUMMARY	7

1. INTRODUCTION

Located in the Mediterranean Sea, an archipelago comprising Malta, Gozo, and Comino, along with the smaller, uninhabited islands of Cominotto, Filfla and St. Paul is situated. Malta's geographic position has been beneficial for both trading and military purposes for centuries. More recently, however, the Maltese Islands have been noted more for their scuba diving than for their long and checkered past. The clear blue Mediterranean Sea offers some unique diving experiences with reefs, caves, and wrecks to explore. To help understand and expand the scuba diving industry, this research sought to investigate the activity on the island by conducting a supply side analysis that included interviews with dive operators operating on Malta, Gozo, and Comino. This research forms part of the Green Bubbles Rise Project. The Green Bubbles project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 643712. Please note that this report reflects only the researchers' view. The Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

2. PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY

A staff member from NWU conducted the research in Malta. Interviews were conducted with nine operators during August 2016. Valuable insights regarding the business profiles, key management aspects, SWOT analysis of the operations as well as the need for an MPA were obtained (semi-structured interviews). Descriptive statistics were used to profile the respondents. The interviews were transcribed into text and presented in a narrative form. Creswell's six steps in data analysis and interpretation were used to analyse the data. These included: Step 1 – Organise and prepare the data; Step 2 – Read through all the data; Step 3 – Begin a detailed analysis of a coding process; Step 4 – Use the coding process to generate a description of the setting or people as well as categories or themes for analysis; Step 5 – Propose the description and themes represented in the qualitative narrative; and Step 6 – Make an interpretation of or explain the meaning of the data (Creswell, 2009). Trustworthiness for this study was accomplished by means of peer examination, coding, and recoding the data. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the North-West University (Potchefstroom Campus: NWU-).

Consent was furthermore obtained from all participants before the interviews were conducted. The different parties were requested to grant permission to ensure informed and voluntary participation. All the participants were also advised that their identity would be protected and that they could withdraw from the research project at any time.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Demographic profile of the dive operators

Section A was developed to capture the demographic information of the dive operators and the results are presented in Table 1 below.

All of the respondents were male, aged 47 years on average, with some form of formal education. Fifty-five percent (55%) were from Malta and were also married. Fifty-five percent grew up by the sea and 33% grew up inland. This shows that the dive operations industry in Malta is dominated by married males over the age of 40.

Table 1: Demographic profile of the dive operators

Aspects	2016 results
SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION	
Gender	Male (100%)
Age	Average age of 47 years
Marital status	Married (55%)
Origin	Malta (55%)
Level of qualification	Graduate (33%), master's degree (22%) diploma (22%)
Grew up	By the sea (55%), inland (33%)

3.2 Details of the dive operators

Section B was developed to capture the information regarding the details of the charter and included the following questions as presented in Table 2:

Question 1 (Q1): *How many years have you been in operation as a dive operator?* Three respondents have been operators for over 20 years, with two being in operation for over 40 and 30 years, respectively and two had only been in operation for less than 10 years.

Question 2 (Q2): *How many boats do you have in operation?* Only one respondent has five boats, while four have one boat each and the other four indicated that they use “dive trucks”.

Question 3 (Q3): *How many staff do you employ?* The number of staff employed could indicate the size of the business. The number of employees, both permanent and contract, varies between three and 20 employees per operator. The reason for this variation could be due to a number of factors such as the size of the business, seasonality, business requirements, to name but a few. .

Question 4 (Q4): *How much do you charge per dive?* The participants charge an average of €33 per dive. The different pricing for each participant is indicated in Table 2.

Question 5 (Q5): *Do you offer technical or recreational dives?* Five of the participants offer both recreational and technical dives, while the other four only offer recreational dives.

Question 6 (Q6): *Do you attend any marketing shows?* Five attend marketing shows, while the remaining four indicated that they did not attend any shows.

Question 7 (Q7): *Who is your main target market?* For the participants, the main target market is foreigners mainly from Europe, mostly the United Kingdom, Germany, France and Italy. A low percentage of not more than 10% is the local target market.

Question 8 (Q8): *How many dives and courses have been registered by your charter in the last six years?* This was to establish whether the operators offer training, and seven indicated that they did offer training in the last six years, while the other two noted that they did not.

Table 2: Details of the charter

	Resp't 1	Resp't 2	Resp't t 3	Resp't 4	Resp't 5	Resp't 6	Resp't 7	Resp't 8	Resp't 9
Years in operation	More than 30 years in the business	More than 40 years in the business	More than 10 years in the business	More than 10 years in the business	More than 20 years in the business	More than 20 years in the business	6 years in the business	5 years in the business	More than 20 years in the business
Boats	1 boat	2 boats	1 boat	None	None	1	1 boat	None	5 boats
Permanent staff	7 permanent staff	15 permanent staff	8 permanent staff	6 permanent staff	5 permanent staff	20 permanent staff	18 permanent staff	3 permanent staff	10 permanent staff
Contract workers	7	-	-	8	-	-	-	-	-
Prices	€48	€40	€45	€40	€40	€28	€35	€30	€38
Months of diving operations	12 months	8 months	8 months	12 months					
Recreational or technical dives	Both	Both	Recreational	Recreational	Both	Recreational	Both	Both	Recreational
Training	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	-	Yes	Yes
Website	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Marketing shows	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Marketing tools	Word of mouth	-	Print media, word of mouth	Presentations locally	Magazines, internet	Word of mouth, social media, dive shows, website	-	-	-
Markets	Foreign 80% Locals 10%	Scandanavians	Europe	Foreign (European)	Holland, UK	Foreign (UK, Germany, Italy)	-	-	Foreign and local

3.3 Key success factors

Section C of the questionnaire focused on the main objective of this study, which is, to determine the critical success factors. The respondents were asked to indicate the critical success factors of their business, and these factors were then grouped into the following themes

Theme 1: Qualities of company

The independent aspects in this factor mentioned by respondents 1 and 4 were honesty and persistence. This reflects the personal values of the respondents

Theme 2: Quality service

Participants 1, 3 and 7 mentioned aspects such as safety, attention to detail and quality of the team. These are important because tourists are more likely to visit a place where their safety is assured, where their

needs and specification will be paid attention to and lastly a place that has a workforce who delivers the highest level of service.

Theme 3: Location and well established

Two of the participants (6 and 8) indicated that location was a key success factor, which is why they are located at convenient areas. For participant 8, they are the only diving centre in the area, which is a great advantage because of a lack of competition. When a destination is easily accessible, it is more likely to be successful and attract more tourists. Participants 1 and 6 indicated that the business was well known and well established, which means that they have built a market base over the years and get a great deal of word-of-mouth marketing. This was indicated by being in the business for over 25 years.

Theme 4: Well-trained staff members

This was the most important for most of the participants with five of them agreeing that a well-trained workforce is a critical success factor. Participants 1, 2, 6, 7 and 9 stressed the importance of having well-trained, professional, experienced and well-managed staff. Members of staff are the ambassadors of the business in- and outside the workplace, especially front-line employees, as they are the first people the tourists interact with when they get to the business.

Theme 5: Personal relations with customers

Five participants (3, 5, 6, 7 and 9) also noted that personal service was important to the success of the business. Personal relations with customers ensure satisfaction and loyalty, which lead to positive word-of-mouth referrals. The aspects mentioned by the participants were few divers per instructor, personal relationship with customers, repeat and loyal customers, offer dives in winter for no financial gain to build relationships with the divers, offer custom packages (tailored services for different types of divers) and offer a high level of unique service to divers.

Theme 6: Passion and conservation

Participants 1 and 7 mentioned that the passion for diving and the sea, having marine protection credentials and not offering unguided dives were success factors for them. Having a passion for what you do propels you to be conservative, in this case protecting marine resources. This comes as an advantage because tourists are increasingly becoming concerned about tourism activities on the environment.

3.4 SWOT analysis

In this section, the participants were asked to indicate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in their businesses. The results are illustrated in Figure 1 on the next page.

Apart from being considered a critical success factor, location was considered as a **strength** by participants 1 and 2, while participants 7, 8 and 9 mentioned training of staff, flexibility and reputation/integrity of the business. New equipment and local knowledge were mentioned by participants 3 and 4. Four of the participants (3, 5, 6 and 8) indicated that they have no plans for expansion as an answer for the **opportunities** question. For the other participants, opportunities include offering or increasing technical dives, entering new markets, offering career development services and using a different approach to operations.

Most of the participants agree that the lack of marine life and its conservation thereof are a **threat** to the dive operations industry. Another concern was the issue of unlicensed/illegal operators, where, in some instances, deaths have occurred because of this. Another threat is illegal fishing and for one participant competition from other dive centres. The dive operators are no exception to **weaknesses** and therefore mentioned the following in this regard; high staff turnover, teamwork can be a problem, not enough time to train staff well, seasonality and not enough staff leading to the staff not being able to take time off.

Figure 1: SWOT analysis

4. SUMMARY

- One of the biggest problems experienced during the interview process is finding an updated list of dive centres/operators on the island, which was absent or outdated on the Internet. This highlights the fact the majority of operators do not regard internet marketing as important, but rely on word-of-mouth and personal relationships with divers.
- Respondents have different opinions of what a dive centre, operator, agency or association entails due to the lack of guidelines of an MPA regarding these businesses.
- Most indicated that their businesses are doing well financially, but emphasised the seasonality of the business.
- All interviewees mentioned three CSFs: Passion for diving, location and having a personal relationship with clients, which correlate with findings from Portofino and Ponta do Ouro.
- While it is clear that the dive season is short, very few centres are looking to expand their operations beyond the season. Some mentioned introducing snorkelling and offering boat excursions, but do not market the activities efficiently to potentially attract other markets. Focus is also not necessarily on attracting new divers – rather retaining current clients.
- Challenges faced by Malta operators were mentioned to include the following:
 - Lack of support for the industry
 - The need for enforcement – unlicensed individuals/entities that operate with fewer costs and then compete on price
 - Price competition
 - Lack of marketing,
 - At national level (MTA), internationally
 - To create awareness of our seas even at a local level
 - Lack of novelties (Grand Thornton, 2016)
- The desire to enrol as part of an association is of paramount importance, as it gives the sector further strength when:
 - dealing with Government
 - making the industry's voice heard
 - combatting illegalities that exist within the industry
 - carrying out combined marketing whereby the industry at large is promoted
- Does not have the infrastructure to accommodate disabled divers – the island is also not disability friendly. Having the support of an MPA could address this problem.
- Fishing is a big problem (fishermen are not interested in conservation or sustainability. With the help of an MPA, areas could be enforced for fishing to help with the conservation of the dive sites).
- Comino was proposed as a possible area for an MPA.

It was clear from the data gathered that all the operators feel very strongly about the need for an MPA to enforce guidelines and regulations for the conservation of the marine life and to provide support in operating their dive operations.